

Relationship of Arm Acupressure Points and Thai Traditional Massage

Authors : Boonyarat Chaleephay

Abstract : The purpose of this research paper was to describe the relationship of acupressure points on the anterior surface of the upper limb in accordance with Applied Thai Traditional Massage (ATTM) and the deep structures located at those acupressure points. There were 2 population groups; normal subjects and cadaver specimens. Eighteen males with age ranging from 20-40 years old and seventeen females with ages ranging from 30-97 years old were studied. This study was able to obtain a fundamental knowledge concerning acupressure point and the deep structures that related to those acupressure points. It might be used as the basic knowledge for clinically applying and planning treatment as well as teaching in ATTM.

Keywords : acupressure point (AP), applied Thai traditional medicine (ATTM), paresthesia, numbness

Conference Title : ICEIT 2014 : International Conference on Educational and Instructional Technology

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : January 20-21, 2014